

NATIONAL AND COMMON TO ALL MANKIND UNIVERSAL IDEAS BASED ON THE RICH HERITAGE OF ANCESTORS

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***Abstract.** In the complex times, when globalization is accelerating in the world development, where drastic changes are taking place, studying, analyzing and determining the place of national and universal qualities in moral education, educating the young generation is a historical necessity and a demand of the times. Deep and comprehensive study of national and universal qualities in modern conditions, correct determination of their place and role in the education of the young generation, specific connections between them, customs, rituals, rules it is important to determine the relationship between them. In this article, ideas about national and universal values that are inherited from generation to generation are put forward.*

***Keywords:** national and common to all mankind universal qualities, national traditions, family, neighborhood, moral culture.*

Increasing the efficiency of the measures implemented today regarding educational reforms, raising the intellectual potential, consciousness and worldview of young people, strengthening their ideological immunity, patriotism, the essence of the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan and the conditions created for young people One of the urgent issues is to study the principles of raising a mature generation that has a deep understanding, is competitive in all aspects, has a broad worldview, has an independent opinion, and lives with a sense of love and loyalty to its people. As the head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoev, noted, “If the body of society’s life is the economy, then its soul and spirit is spirituality. We will build a new Uzbekistan on these two strong pillars, that is, a strong economy based on market principles and the rich heritage of our ancestors, national and common to all mankind universal ideals. We rely on the strong spirituality that embodies it” [1]. After gaining independence, the interest of our people to know the history of their country, language, culture, and values, and to understand their identity, increased. This is a natural state. There are people who are interested in knowing who their ancestors are, their lineage, and the history of the country where they were born and grew up.

In order for young people to be **leaders** in all fields, they should first of all have **good manners**. Because, according to Islamic teachings, manners are one of the main means of reaching the blessings of the hereafter. Both the Holy Quran and the hadiths of the Prophet (peace be upon him) pay special attention to the issue of manners. Much has been written about parenting. But this topic is always relevant and important from the point of view of protecting young people from various attacks that come in such as “mass culture”.

At present, some divisive forces are instilling in the minds of young people the most dangerous vices that are completely foreign to our spirituality and morality, including misinterpreted religious teachings, to alienate them from their parents, family and loved ones, to read or to remove them from work and to send them to countries where armed conflicts are going on, to turn them into militants or “living bombs”.

“Cultures” destroys the spiritual life of the society, has a serious negative impact on the morals, outlook, and upbringing of young people.

How many great scientists, noblemen, scholars, politicians, and generals have grown from this ancient and blessed soil. The foundations of most religious and secular sciences were created and polished on this land.

It is natural for every person to ask himself the following questions: I am a **child of this nation, who were my ancestors**, what was the origin of my nation, how did it stand up, recover, and form?

This nation contributed its indelible share to the development of the people, spread the fame of our country to the world, and was forever imprinted on the pages of history. Our land has always been a land of great scholars, thinkers, and geniuses who were ahead of their time. Abu Rayhan Beruni, Ahmad Farghani, Muhammad al-Khorazmi, Mirzo Ulughbek, Ali Kushchi, Abu Nasr Farabi, Alisher Navai, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Mahmud Zamakhshari, Imam Bukhari, Imam Termizi, Abu Bakr Kaffol Shoshi, Abu Mansur Moturidi, Abdukholiq Gijduvani, Bahauddin Naqshband, Abulmuin Nasafi, Burhoniddin Marginani, Imam Dorimi.. the names of them would be a book. One is a teacher of theological sciences, one is a great scientist who put a ladder to the mountain of heaven, another is the father of applied medicine, one is a master of theological sciences, and another is the sultan of scholars [2, 17].

The moral culture in the educational institution is formed by the desire of each member to understand each other through the spiritual image. National and universal qualities are the criteria that show his honor, pride, duties and tasks. A sense of pure lineage and pride in it ultimately creates patriotism and nationalistic pride. Mutual respect in the team is one of the important criteria for all students to fulfill their duties and tasks based on strict discipline, to show kindness and kindness to each other. Within the framework of national virtues, honoring the honor of the family, neighborhood, and Motherland over one's own well-being, giving priority to caring for one's relatives and loved ones, one's neighbors - is considered a high-level virtue. In the course of the lesson, in the territory of the boarding school, the issue of discipline is of great importance in the determination of national qualities. Along with class discipline, family discipline is the foundation of society and state discipline. Because the student who has developed a sense of discipline in the lesson will serve in the state and society in the future as a possessor of this feeling, he will not even think about breaking the laws of the state, he will determine each work in its place and time, based on order. does. Such discipline and order become the honor of the people and the nation today. Each member of the specialized boarding school community has a culture of ethics and internal discipline based on this, along with an understanding of their duties and responsibilities, so that they can determine their place in any environment in the future, and respect their interpersonal relationships. , helps the formation of qualities such as the family's economic capabilities, striving to ensure the interests of the Motherland, honoring the honor of the Motherland. The uniqueness of this or that people as a nation shines in this national quality. Competences in students by forming the national qualities that have been formed in the family in the lessons of boarding schools, enriching the content and effectiveness of education, as well as instilling national and universal qualities in the minds of students. In addition to educating students with good virtues, it is also necessary to list the negative qualities that undermine the perfection of a person (evil, ignorance, lying, vulgarity, etc.) At the heart of national qualities, first of all, the student considers the culture, values, and history of his people. Based on the study of religion, the

heritage of the past generations, material and spiritual wealth, it opens the way to educate universal human qualities.

In the process of education, in the education of national and universal qualities in students, the goal of the lesson is to create a healthy environment through the culture of creativity, activity and communication, and to achieve the education of good qualities in order to achieve the realization of the student's identity. possible In this regard, O. Musurmonova's research is noteworthy. The scientist tries to solve a number of pedagogical problems regarding the formation of the spiritual culture of high school students. O. Musurmonova points out "In our opinion, the inner spiritual world of a person consists of a system of basic signs such as spiritual need, spiritual interest, spiritual activity, and spiritual value"[3, 23]. In Sh.A.Abdullaeva and D.I.Rozieva's work of "Pedagogical diagnosis and correction", students are taught to be loyal to the Motherland, kind to people and believe in national and universal human values, artistic and artistic works as a national and universal competence. It is defined as the ability to understand, dress modestly, follow cultural rules and a healthy lifestyle [4, 221].

Pedagogical requirements for educating students with national and universal human virtues - stages of education organization - the main goal of educational science - educational goal with national and universal cultural competence - selection of educational methods and tools appropriate to the topic - sources of folk pedagogy - The heritage of Central Asian thinkers - national and universal values can enrich modern pedagogic science according to its uniqueness and value. At the same time, the science of pedagogy must also use its tools, it undergoes changes, acquires a new appearance and content, characteristic or purpose that is acceptable for a certain period of people's life and is passed from generation to generation. . Their pedagogical value is that if these national values are not a guide in life, we lose our most important human qualities.

After all, lifestyle, way of life, manners, communication, behavior are fed by national qualities. Therefore, if national qualities do not take place in human life, humanity gradually loses its human form, bad behavior, immorality becomes the basis of communication between people, carelessness, thoughtlessness, rudeness, obscenities appear at every turn. All this testifies to the essence and importance of national qualities in the life of a person and the whole society.

Therefore, the question arises about the need to study and promote the qualities formed on the basis of progressive, democratic national values by studying and promoting the pedagogical ideas of folk and ethnic pedagogy, because its Its ideas are based on the people's life, it is to protect their interests, to educate them in all aspects of life. Consequently, the people, on the one hand, strives to follow his pedagogical ideas in raising their children, and on the other hand, based on his recommendations, they decide their lifestyle, behavior, behavior, morals and ethics.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. «Yangi O'zbekistonning 2022–2026 yillarga mo'ljallangan Taraqqiyot strategiyasi»-2022-yil 10-yanvar PF-60./www.lex.uz
2. Tarbiyachi va pedagoglar uchun qo'llanma. Prezident ta'lim muasasalarini agentligi – T.: 2022. 66 bet, 17-b
3. Musurmonova O. Oila ma'naviyati - milliy g'urur. –T.: O'qituvchi, 1999. 200 bet, 23-b
4. Sh.A.Abdullaeva D.I.Ro'ziyeva. Pedagogik diagnostika va korrektsiya.-T.: O'qituvchi, 2018.265 bet, 221-b

